

Supplemental Material for

Life-long creatine deficiency leads to augmented sarcoplasmic reticulum calcium release but not heart failure

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This supplemental material has Figures S1–S7.

Figure S1. Similar dyssynchrony of Ca^{2+} transients in cardiomyocytes from AGAT KO and WT littermates. The same data as in Fig 1 was analyzed. A summary of statistical analysis by linear mixed models is depicted below the graph. A: Two examples showing synchronous (left) and dyssynchronous (right) Ca^{2+} release in AGAT KO cardiomyocytes. The half-maximal amplitude before the local fluorescence maxima is denoted by black lines. The variability of the detected lines in time was used to calculate the systolic dyssynchrony index. B: The systolic dyssynchrony index (larger value corresponds to more dyssynchrony) is shown in a logarithmic scale (base 10), with a larger value corresponding to a more dyssynchronous transient. There was no difference between AGAT KO and WT, but ISO treatment led to more synchronous Ca^{2+} transients. As the contribution of solution was significant for all analyzed measurements, the contribution of the genotype and sex was determined by including solution into the null model.

Figure S2. The ratio of spark amplitudes for the sparks occurring in the same location (within $0.5 \mu\text{m}$) as a function of the delay between sparks. Here, AGAT KO and WT were compared. There was no significant difference in the time constants, possibly due to the relatively small number of spark pairs occurring in WT cardiomyocytes. The data is from the same experiment as shown in Fig 2.

Figure S3. Representative Western blot experiments to assess the expression of RyR and phospholamban (PLB) and their phosphorylated forms. The animal genotype and sex are shown above each lane. REF is the reference sample to which the other samples were compared, allowing us to compare results from different blots. A: GAPDH was used as loading control. B: Total PLB expression. C: PLB phosphorylated at Ser-16. D: PLB phosphorylated at Thr-17. E: Total RyR expression. F: RyR phosphorylated at Ser-2808. G: RyR phosphorylated at Ser-2814. For each antibody, different dilutions of the primary and secondary antibodies were tested to ensure proportionality of the signal with the amount of protein in a separate series of experiments. Samples were loaded in random sequence, with the sequence varied between repetitions to avoid bias.

Figure S4. Data from Western blot experiments to assess the expression of RyR and phospholamban (PLB) and their phosphorylated forms in AGAT. Expression levels were related to overall expression in WT (male and female pulled together). A, B, C: Expression of RyR (A), PKA-phosphorylated RyR (Ser2808, B), and CaMKII-phosphorylated RyR (Ser2814, C). D, E: Phosphorylation of RyR related to overall expression of RyR. F, G, H: PLB (F) and phosphorylated PLB in sites corresponding to PKA phosphorylation (Ser16, G) and CaMKII phosphorylation (Thr17, H). I, J: Phosphorylation of PLB related to overall expression of PLB. For each sample, Western blot experiments were repeated 3-7 times. For data shown in each panel, levels were compared between sexes for WT and KO separately, between genotype for each sex separately using either linear mixed models (A, B, C, F, G, H) taking into account multiple measurements from the same sample or using t-test (D, E, I, J). Statistical results are shown for p values smaller than 0.15, significance indicated in bold. The number of animals used in the experiments was as follows: AGAT WT female (5), AGAT WT male (6), AGAT KO female (5), AGAT KO male (6).

Figure S5. Same data as in Fig S4, but with the expression levels related to GAPDH expression in the samples, i.e. with GAPDH serving as a loading control. A: GAPDH expression used as a reference. B-F: RyR and its phosphorylated forms either related to GAPDH expression (B-D) or, after taking into account measured GAPDH in each sample, to overall RyR expression (E, F). G-K: PLB and its phosphorylated forms analyzed the same way as RyR in B-F.

Figure S6. Representative Western blots of S100A1 and BIN1, and the Ponceau image from the BIN1 blot. The S100A1 band was close to 10 kDa as indicated by the arrows. The BIN1 blot had several unspecific bands, and we analyzed the band near 50 kDa as indicated by the arrows. The animal genotype and sex are shown above each lane. REF is the reference sample to which the other samples were compared, allowing us to compare results from different blots.

Figure S7. Representative Western blots of LKB1, AMPK, and phosphorylated AMPK (pAMPK), and the Ponceau image from the pAMPK blot. The LKB1 band was close to 55 kDa as indicated by the arrows. AMPK and pAMPK were found near 60 kDa as indicated by the arrows. The animal genotype and sex are shown above each lane. REF is the reference sample to which the other samples were compared, allowing us to compare results from different blots.